

Studies in the Synthesis of Anticancer Agents : Part V¹ : Nitrogen Mustards of Quinoline Derivatives

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p-[N,N-bis(2-Chloroethyl)-amino]-benzaldehyde on condensation with hydrazide derivatives of 2-(4'-carboxyphenyl amino)-4-methyl quinolines, 2-(2'-carboxy phenyl amino)-4-methyl quinolines, 4-(4'-carboxy phenyl amino)-2-methyl quinolines, 4-(2'-carboxy phenyl amino)-2-methyl quinolines gave nitrogen mustards (IIa), (IIb), (IIIa) and (IIIe), respectively. These compounds were tested for anticancer activity against Rat Walker 256 carcinosarcoma.

In recent years, considerable interest has been created in the antimalarial nitrogen mustards as potent chemotherapeutic agents for the cancer treatment. Elderfield *et al.*² have synthesised nitrogen mustards from quinoline derivatives as potential anticancer agents. W. Schulze *et al.*³ synthesised new Schiff-bases and tried to establish the correlation between chemical structure and biological activity against the "Ehrlich ascites" tumor of azomethines containing the nitrogen mustard group. Thus they have prepared 4-[N-[*p*-bis(2-chloroethyl)-amino-phenyl]-formimidoyl]-1-methyl quinolinium iodide oxide (I), and found that it is most strongly active against "Ehrlich ascites" carcinoma in AB/Jena mice.

We report here the synthesis of large number of quinoline derivatives by condensing *p*-[N,N-bis(2-chloroethyl)-amino]benzaldehyde with different hydrazide derivatives of 2-(4'-carboxy phenyl amino)-4-methyl quinolines, 2-(2'-carboxy phenyl amino)-4-methyl quinolines, 4-(4'-carboxy phenyl amino)-2-methyl quinolines, 4-(2'-carboxy phenyl amino)-2-methyl quinolines to give (IIa), (IIb), (IIIa) and (IIIe) respectively.

2-Chloro-4-methyl quinoline derivatives were condensed with *p*-amino benzoic acid in 2*N* HCl solution to give 2-(4'-carboxy phenyl amino)-4-methyl quinoline derivatives, according to the method of El-Agamy *et al.*⁴, which on esterification gave 2-(4'-carboxy phenyl amino)-4-methyl quinoline derivatives. These esters on treatment with hydrazine hydrate gave 2-(4'-carboxy phenyl amino)-4-methyl quinoline derivatives which when condensed with mustard aldehyde gave (IIa). Similarly derivatives of (IIb) were synthesised by condensing 2-chloro-4-methyl quinoline derivatives with *o*-amino benzoic acid, followed by esterification, treatment with hydrazine hydrate and condensation with mustard aldehyde.

4-chloro 2-methyl quinoline derivatives on similar series of reactions with *o*- and *p*- amino benzoic acid gave (IIIa) and (IIIe) respectively.

(IIa) $R_1 = 4' - \text{CO-NH-N}=\text{CH}-\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{Cl})_2$, $R = \text{H}$

(IIb) $R_1 = 2' - \text{CO-NH-N}=\text{CH}-\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{Cl})_2$, $R = \text{H}$

(IIIa) $R = 6\text{-methoxy}$, $R_1 = 4' - \text{CO-NH-N}=\text{CH}-\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{Cl})_2$

(IIIb) $R = 7\text{-chloro}$, $R_1 = 4' - \text{CO-NH-N}=\text{CH}-\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{Cl})_2$

(IIIc) $R = 8\text{-chloro}$, $R_1 = 4' - \text{CO-NH-N}=\text{CH}-\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{Cl})_2$

(III d) $R = 6\text{-chloro}$, $R_1 = 4' - \text{CO-NH-N}=\text{CH}-\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{Cl})_2$

(III e) $R = 7\text{-chloro}$, $R_1 = 2' - \text{CO-NH-N}=\text{CH}-\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{Cl})_2$

(III f) $R = 8\text{-chloro}$, $R_1 = 2' - \text{CO-NH-N}=\text{CH}-\text{N}(\text{C}_2\text{H}_4\text{Cl})_2$

Biological activity :

The compounds III-a, III-b, III-c, III-d, III-e, and III-f were tested against Rat Walker 256 carcinosarcoma and were found to be inactive.

Experimental

(1) *Synthesis of 2-(4'-(p-N,N-bis(2-Chloroethyl)-amino-benzylidene) hydrazino carbonyl phenyl amino)-4-methyl quinoline derivatives :*

A mixture of 2-chloro-4-methyl quinoline (2.0 g) and *p*-amino benzoic acid (1.5 g) in 2*N* HCl solution (25.0 ml) were refluxed on sand bath for 6 hr. to give 2-(4'-carboxy phenyl amino)-4-methyl quinoline hydrochloride (2.5 g). This was dissolved in absolute ethanol (100.0 ml) previously made

saturated with dry HCl gas and was refluxed on water bath for 15 hr. The separated hydrochloride of ester was dissolved in water and neutralised with 10.0% Na₂CO₃ solution to obtain free ester (2.0 g). The ester (2.0 g) was refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (10.0 ml) in ethanol (25.0 ml) for 16 hr on water bath to give 2-(4'-hydrazino carbonyl phenyl amino)-4-methyl quinoline (1.8 g). The hydrazide derivative (1.5 g) on further condensation with mustard aldehyde (1.5 g) in ethanol (25.0 ml) gave (IIa), (2.1 g). It was crystallised from ethanol (Tables 1 and 2).

The above series of reactions were performed on 2-chloro-4-methyl quinoline with *o*-aminobenzoic acid and also on 2-methyl-4-chloro quinolines with *o*- and *p*- amino benzoic acid (Tables 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 and 8).

TABLE 1—2-(4'-CARBOXYL PHENYLAMINO)-4-METHYL-QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES

R	R ₁	M.P.	Found				Molecular formula	Required			
			C%	H%	N%	Cl%		C%	H%	N%	Cl%
H	-o-C ₆ H ₅	182	74.60	6.35	9.10	—	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	74.50	5.883	9.15	—
H	-NH-NH ₂	254	69.57	5.12	19.08	—	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	69.85	5.480	19.18	—
8-methyl	-o-C ₆ H ₅	199	74.59	6.67	8.89	—	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	75.00	6.250	8.75	—
8-methyl	-NH-NH ₂	286	70.53	6.38	18.94	—	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	70.50	5.883	18.30	—
6-methyl	-o-C ₆ H ₅	222	74.50	6.67	8.81	—	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	75.00	6.25	8.75	—
6-methyl	-NH-NH ₂	261	70.26	6.35	17.95	—	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	70.50	5.883	18.30	—
6-Chloro	-o-C ₆ H ₅	110	66.51	4.39	8.75	9.98	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	66.96	4.992	8.22	10.43
6-Chloro	-NH-NH ₂	220	62.18	4.77	17.10	10.57	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ OCl	62.20	4.573	17.07	10.82

TABLE 2—2-(4'-(p-N,N-BIS-(2-CHLOROETHYL)AMINO BENZYLIDENE)HYDRAZINOCARBONYL-PHENYLAMINO)-4-METHYL-QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES

R	M.P.	Found				Molecular formula	Required			
		C%	H%	N%	Cl%		C%	H%	N%	Cl%
H	220	65.04	5.19	12.97	14.16	C ₂₉ H ₂₇ N ₅ OCl ₂	64.62	5.19	13.46	13.66
8-methyl	230	65.24	6.50	13.60	13.59	C ₂₉ H ₂₉ N ₅ OCl ₂	65.20	5.43	13.11	13.30
6-methyl	222	64.98	5.26	12.74	13.73	C ₂₉ H ₂₉ N ₅ OCl ₂	65.20	5.43	13.11	13.30
6-Chloro	162	60.40	4.25	12.98	19.37	C ₂₉ H ₂₅ N ₅ OCl ₃	60.60	4.69	12.62	19.20

TABLE 3—2-(2'-CARBOXYL PHENYLAMINO)-4-METHYL-QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES

R	R ₁	M.P.	Found				Molecular formula	Required			
			C%	H%	N%	Cl%		C%	H%	N%	Cl%
H	-o-C ₆ H ₅	130	74.33	5.73	9.07	—	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	74.50	5.883	9.15	—
H	-NH-NH ₂	222	69.44	5.97	19.65	—	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O	69.85	5.48	19.18	—
6-methyl	-o-C ₆ H ₅	173	74.50	6.57	8.43	—	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	75.00	6.25	8.75	—
6-methyl	-NH-NH ₂	241	70.18	6.38	18.41	—	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	70.50	5.883	18.30	—
8-methyl	-o-C ₆ H ₅	132	74.50	6.42	8.76	—	C ₂₀ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	75.00	6.25	8.75	—
8-methyl	-NH-NH ₂	178	70.42	6.32	18.00	—	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₂ O	70.50	5.883	18.30	—
6-Chloro	-o-C ₆ H ₅	168	66.96	4.72	8.00	10.78	C ₁₉ H ₁₇ N ₂ O ₂ Cl	66.96	4.992	8.22	10.43
6-Chloro	-NH-NH ₂	225	62.40	4.55	17.00	10.75	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ OCl	62.20	4.573	17.07	10.82

TABLE 4—2-(2'-(p-N,N-BIS(2-CHLOROETHYL)AMINO BENZYLIDINE) HYDRAZINOCARBONYL-PHENYLAMINO)-4-METHYL QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES

R	M.P.	Found				Molecular formula	Required			
		C%	H%	N%	Cl%		C%	H%	N%	Cl%
H	101	65.10	5.65	13.12	14.10	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ N ₃ OCl ₂	64.62	5.19	13.46	13.66
8-methyl	191	65.70	5.86	12.67	13.68	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ OCl ₂	65.20	5.43	13.11	13.30
6-methyl	200	65.72	5.85	12.79	13.59	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ OCl ₂	65.20	5.43	13.11	13.30
6-Chloro	158	60.38	4.21	12.90	19.57	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ N ₃ OCl ₃	60.60	4.69	12.62	19.20

TABLE 5—2-METHYL-4-(4'-CARBOXYL PHENYLAMINO) QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES

R	R ₁	M.P.	Found			Molecular formula	Required		
			C%	H%	N%		C%	H%	N%
H	-o-C ₆ H ₅	170	74.20	5.55	9.00	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	74.50	5.88	9.15
H	-NH-NH ₂	268	69.85	5.63	18.70	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O	69.85	5.48	19.18
6-methyl	-o-C ₆ H ₅	208	74.66	6.15	7.98	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	75.00	6.25	8.75
6-methyl	-NH-NH ₂	245	70.21	6.01	18.04	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O	70.60	5.88	18.30
8-methyl	-o-C ₆ H ₅	135	74.75	6.02	8.88	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	75.00	6.25	8.75
8-methyl	-NH-NH ₂	273	70.11	6.20	18.25	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O	70.60	5.88	18.30
6-methyl	-o-C ₆ H ₅	262	71.02	5.59	8.00	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	71.44	5.95	8.34
6-methyl	-NH-NH ₂	130	66.88	5.70	17.51	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O	67.10	5.59	17.40
6-ethoxy	-o-C ₆ H ₅	277	71.75	6.17	7.83	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	72.00	6.28	8.00
6-ethoxy	-NH-NH ₂	265	68.09	5.22	16.78	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O	67.86	5.95	16.61

TABLE 6—2-METHYL-4-(2'-CARBOXYL PHENYLAMINO) QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES

R	R ₁	M.P.	Found			Molecular formula	Required		
			C%	H%	N%		C%	H%	N%
H	-o-C ₆ H ₅	107	74.68	6.07	8.76	C ₁₉ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₂	74.50	5.88	9.15
H	-NH-NH ₂	228	69.60	5.69	19.02	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₄ O	69.85	5.48	19.18
6-methyl	-o-C ₆ H ₅	125	75.28	6.67	8.80	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	75.00	6.25	8.75
6-methyl	-NH-NH ₂	265	71.10	5.90	18.80	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O	70.60	5.88	18.30
8-methyl	-o-C ₆ H ₅	110	74.75	6.02	8.88	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	75.00	6.25	8.75
8-methyl	-NH-NH ₂	222	70.11	6.20	18.25	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O	70.60	5.88	18.30
6-methoxy	-o-C ₆ H ₅	110	71.02	5.59	8.00	C ₂₀ H ₁₈ N ₂ O ₂	71.44	5.95	8.34
6-methoxy	-NH-NH ₂	216	66.88	5.70	17.51	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O	67.10	5.59	17.40
6-methoxy	-o-C ₆ H ₅	134	72.50	6.78	8.39	C ₂₁ H ₂₀ N ₂ O ₂	72.00	6.28	8.00
6-ethoxy	-NH-NH ₂	208	67.31	6.32	16.45	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ N ₄ O	67.86	5.95	16.67

TABLE 7—2-METHYL-4-(4'-(p-N,N-BIS(2-CHLOROETHYL)AMINO BENZYLIDINE) HYDRAZINE CARBOXYL-PHENYLAMINO) QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES

R	M.P.	Found				Molecular formula	Required			
		C%	H%	N%	Cl%		C%	H%	N%	Cl%
H	185	64.23	5.84	13.04	13.42	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ OCl ₂	64.62	5.19	13.46	13.66
6-methyl	152 (dec)	65.10	5.95	12.74	13.00	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ OCl ₂	65.20	5.53	13.11	13.30
8-methyl	205-7	65.00	5.75	12.96	13.12	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ OCl ₂	65.20	5.53	13.11	13.30
6-methoxy	190 (dec)	63.09	5.55	12.57	13.03	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₂	63.28	5.27	12.73	12.91
6-ethoxy	160 (dec)	63.00	6.06	12.10	12.73	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₂	63.83	5.49	12.41	12.60
6-chloro	192 (dec)	60.10	5.12	12.80	19.12	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₃ OCl ₃	60.60	4.69	12.62	19.20
7-chloro	132 (dec)	60.12	5.00	12.35	19.00	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₃ OCl ₃	60.60	4.69	12.62	19.20
8-chloro	147 (dec)	60.47	5.00	12.37	18.98	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₃ OCl ₃	60.60	4.69	12.62	19.20

TABLE 8—2-METHYL-4-(2'-(p-N,N-BIS(2-CHLOROETHYL)AMINO BENZYLIDINE) HYDRAZINOCARBONYL-PHENYLAMINO) QUINOLINE DERIVATIVES

R	M.P.	Found				Molecular formula	Required			
		C%	H%	N%	Cl%		C%	H%	N%	Cl%
H	228	64.12	5.32	13.29	13.13	C ₂₂ H ₁₇ N ₃ OCl ₂	64.62	5.19	13.46	13.66
6-methyl	147 (dec)	65.84	5.97	12.61	13.45	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ OCl ₂	65.20	5.43	13.11	13.30
8-methyl	195	65.44	5.55	12.20	13.09	C ₂₄ H ₁₉ N ₃ OCl ₂	65.20	5.43	13.11	13.30
6-methoxy	135	63.40	5.12	12.50	12.98	C ₂₂ H ₁₉ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₂	63.28	5.27	12.73	12.91
6-ethoxy	170	63.40	5.95	11.98	12.12	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₃ O ₂ Cl ₂	63.83	5.49	12.41	12.60
8-chloro	140 (dec)	60.26	5.15	12.18	19.12	C ₂₂ H ₁₆ N ₃ OCl ₃	60.68	4.69	12.62	19.20

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